

2017

International Research Journal of Management Sociology & Humanities

Vol 8 Issue 1

ISSN 2348 – 9359

www.IRJMSH.COM

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FARMERS' SUICIDES AS A FALLOUT OF GLOBALIZATION IN ANDHRA PRADESH

[A Study on Farmers' Suicides In Anantapuramu District Of Andhra Pradesh)

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: It is a fact that Globalization has brought in technological and economic advancements that are sweeping across the societies on the globe, but the condition of the rural areas and particularly the condition of farmers continues to be gloomy and a cause for concern. Price fluctuations and the persistent drought conditions or natural calamities add on to the misery of the farmers in one way or the other. Beginning with 27 suicides in 1987, in Warangal and Guntur districts 98 in 1997 and it spiraled to 900 Farmers suicides in 2004-05 as reported by the Government Of Andhra Pradesh. As on March 2005, the Revenue department in Andhra Pradesh has registered, as many as 1395 suicides connected to agriculture and allied activities.

Emile Durkheim who did pioneering work on suicides in the Nineteenth century typified suicides in the modern society as mainly that of Egoistic and Anomic. The other two types being the Altruistic and the Fatalistic, which are not relevant here. The Farmers Suicides in Andhra Pradesh in particular can be included in the Chronic Economic Suicides precipitated by the prolonged phase of economic distress which drives people to suicide in utmost desperation and agonizing economic condition. It is indeed pathetic to see the 'Anna Dathaa' take away his life in utmost frustration never experienced before on the Indian soil. Misery has not been new to the Indian farmer but the swiftly changing economic scenario forced by the Economic reforms and the economic forces that it has unleashed have transformed the world towards a global market, where the poor and the lagging societies are bound to get socially excluded and buckle in the process. Farmers' suicides in Andhra Pradesh are typical examples of the anomic suicides sequel to being caught in the tsunami of globalization socially and economically excluded.

Objective: This paper seeks to unearth the causes and the contributing conditions that brought forth the pathological incidence of Farmers' suicides in the state of Andhra Pradesh in general and Anantapur district in particular as a sequel to the process of Globalization set in the 1990s and which has ended in the meltdown being experienced world wide.

Method of Study: This paper is based on the study on the 200 Farmers who committed suicides during the years 2000-2005 in the Anantapur district of Andhra Pradesh.

Conclusion: This paper draws the conclusion that miseries are not new to the Indian farmer. The forces that were unleashed by the series of economic reforms beginning with the structural adjustments Import policy, disinvestment, privatization, liberalization and globalization which have all rendered the State as helpless agency to the miseries of the farmers due to the commitments it had made to IMF, WTO and GATT. Agriculture being the tradition bound, value and sentiments ridden, farmer folks found the anomic economic situation further precipitated by the natural calamities, found themselves in a debt trap. Being socially excluded from the emerging global economic scenario, these simple, sensitive and poor farmer folk found solace in suicides in utmost frustration without any hand to redeem them from the whirlpool of debt and more than that the status loss in their own village.

Introduction: Agriculture in India is in shambles. The erstwhile pride of our nation and civilization, is now in an unredeemable situation of chaos and crises. The slogan Jai Jawan, Jai Kisan is no more relevant when everyday farmers taking away their lives in desperation. Plagued by the growing costs of cultivation and the vagaries of nature have added on to the miseries of the farmers who are resorting to suicides to escape from the debt bondage. cc Price fluctuations and the persistent drought conditions or natural calamities add on to the misery of the farmers in one way or the other. Beginning with 27 suicides in 1987, in Warangal and Guntur districts 98 in 1997 and it spiraled to 900 Farmers suicides in 2004-05 as reported by the Government Of Andhra Pradesh. As on March 2005, the Revenue department in Andhra Pradesh has registered, as many as 1395 suicides connected to agriculture and allied activities. The incidence of farmers' suicides in Indian states of Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Maharashtra and Punjab has opened the eyes of the public and the government to a pathological situation which is taking the toll of the lives of the farmers.

Suicide is generally considered an individual act. Emile Durkheim who did pioneering work on suicides in the Nineteenth century contends that the spiraling suicide rates all over Europe after Industrialization led him to conclude that suicide is more than an individual act and that larger social forces of integration and social regulation affect it. He typified suicides in the modern

society as mainly that of Egotistic and Anomie. The other two types being the Altruistic and the Fatalistic which are not relevant here. The Farmers Suicides in Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka and Maharashtra, in particular can be included in the Chronic Economic Suicides precipitated by the prolonged phase of economic distress which drives people to suicide in utmost desperation and agonizing economic condition. It is indeed pathetic to see the 'Anna Daataa' take away his life in utmost frustration never experienced before on the Indian soil.

Misery has not been new to the Indian farmer but the swiftly changing economic scenario forced by the Economic reforms and the economic forces that it has unleashed have transformed the world towards a global market, where the poor and the lagging societies are bound to get socially excluded and buckle in the process. Farmers' suicides in Andhra Pradesh are typical examples of the anomic suicides sequel to being caught in the tsunami of globalization socially and economically excluded.

The era of globalization has wrought in sweeping changes across the globe encompassing in every aspect of the lives of the people. The forces it unleashed have resulted in a total transformation of the lifestyles of the people all over the world in tune with western culture and values with high stakes on consumerism. The developing countries were forced into this trap through WTO and GATT encompassing every aspect of peoples lives never seen before the process continued till the recent world wide 'melt down'. The economic reforms that warranted disinvestment and privatization and a limited role for the state as a mere partner have all ended up in a messy recession consequences of which we now find gripping the western world the is going to take the toll of the economies of the world both big and small.

The traditional bastion of Indian society – agriculture was the main casualty of the sweeping changes triggered by globalization. The agrarian activity was engulfed in crises owing to the increasing cost of production, out put prices, inadequate markets and on top of all these liberal policies of importing agricultural products in India. Out put as well as prices stated to fall at the same time. Earlier a fall in production precipitated a rise in the prices. But owing to changes under WTO regime triggered unprecedented changes against the farming community. Numbers of commodities were put on the Open General list. (OGL) of imports. Import tariffs on such commodities were also substantially reduced from 25 per cent to 15 per cent. Maize, pulses, oilseeds, coconut and rubber and arcanut were imported at subsidized costs under the OGL. (Menon, 2002)

Agriculture in the state of Andhra Pradesh is basically associated with small farm cultivation. It is estimated that there are about 10.6 million holdings in the state with an average size of 1.36 hectare per holding. In the total

holdings, small and marginal holdings account to 80.8 per cent. Over the years, the declining crop yields, the small size of the holdings has significant impact on the income levels of agricultural households. The per capita agricultural output recorded a declining trends beginning with 1990s and the cost of cultivation per unit output has been soaring over the years in the state resulted in the decline of the incomes of the farmers forcing them to borrow from private money lenders for the farm activities and family expenditure.

Globalization signaled the ushering in of the forces of the markets, safety nets and the process of commercialization. The humble poor small farmer found caught amidst the current of commercialization without the requisite know how and societal support. Modernization and commercialization and greater use of purchased inputs have made Indian agriculture as no longer a way of life profitable to the farmers. These waves of change with their varying trajectory without corresponding progress in irrigation potential apart from aggravating regional inequalities within the state or even within the district also increased the risk in farming today. The farmer is also greatly exposed to the vicissitudes of market economy with stress on consumerism on one hand and declining institutional supports on the other in the wake of new economic policy ushered in 1991. Added to all this is the role of mass media which evoked rising expectations even among the rural masses for a better way of life Especially the present youth generation small and marginal farmers dissatisfied with their levels of living and with a zeal to improve their lot or also tempted towards commercial crops like cotton, tobacco chilies etc which are vulnerable to multiple risk on many fronts. As a result, these farmers are in the perpetual danger of suffering from disproportions between their expectations and aspirations and real life realities and satisfactions. This restlessness and dissatisfaction has sown seeds of suicidogenic impulses among the farmers.

Farmers' distress and their suicides are not a new phenomenon they are prevalent even prior to the ushering in of market economy in 1991. the first phase of suicides during 1987 -88 among the cotton farmers in Andhra Pradesh is a pointer to this.

The agricultural sector in A.P. which performed well in the 1980s by recording a growth rate of output of 2.67 per cent per annum, showed a decline in its growth rate to 1.16 per cent per annum in the 1990s. Demographic pressures have added to this process of creating marginalization of land holding and thereby affecting the economy viability across the farm groups. More importantly, when the new systems and fresh initiatives were created, enough care has not been taken to provide built in checking mechanisms so as to correct any failures in the process. Extension, credit, input delivery system, input markets, product market mechanisms and the government support schemes, including safety nets, are easily amenable to collapse under the pressure.

Marketing, irrigation Structure etc., is superimposed on an agrarian structure where land institutions are not rationalized. It is an established fact now that the spread of new agriculture technology has not only widened the region imbalances but also disparities among different size and classes of farmers (Bhalla and Tyagi:1989). Cost ratios are some of the disturbing trends which emerged of late on the agrarian scene in india (Vidyasagar and Sumanchandra: 2004) India that can boast about self sufficiency in food production now is wrought with sever problems in terms of sustaining the achievements. For instance, Parthasarathy and Shamcem (1998) studied the suicides of cotton farmers of Warangal district that occurred towards the end of 1997. Muzzaffar Assadi(1998) while analyzing the farmer's suicides in Karnataka observed that committing suicides by farmers was a new phenomenon in Karnataka , Ashish Bose [2000]in his analysis of suicides by Punjab farmers in the cotton belt finds that 85 per cent of the farmers are in the debt and the causes for indebtedness are 1;failure of the cotton crops; Basha (2002) who conducted a study on the suicide farmers of Anantapur district writes that the Anantapur farmer was less distressed, though poor, when he was farming for subsistence. Similarly Narayana (2002), in his analysis of farmer's suicides in Anantapur district points out that the tube-wells frequently dry up due to scant rainfall and the farmers keep training in new areas. . A study undertaken by Vidyasagar and Suman Chandra [2004] highlighted the suicides as the direct consequence of the macro-economic policy changes brought about after 1990.

Objective: This paper seeks to unearth the causes and the contributing conditions that brought forth the pathological incidence of Farmers' suicides in the state of Andra Pradesh in general and Anantapur district in particular as a sequel to the process of Globalization.

Method of Study:

This paper is based on a study of 200 farmers who have committed suicide between 2000 and 2005 in the Anantapur District of Andhra Pradesh. The paper is based on both primary data collected from the families of the farmers who have committed suicide in the district.

Agriculture in the district of Anantapur had been at the mercy of monsoon. Drought had been quite frequent in Rayalaseema region particularly in Anantapur district. The vagaries of nature added to this are the depletion of underwater table resulted in the drying of many of the bore wells upon which the farmers in the district were dependent mostly. The measures of liberalization as part of the economic reforms brought forth unprecedented quantum change forcing the gigantic agriculture to stagger the suicides of the farmers is an indication of the pathological state of agriculture.

Apart from scores of scholars who have studied the farmers suicides, this paper looks at the farmers suicides more as a sociological problem precipitated by the economic reforms which has swept the society at large and the farming community in particular in a trajectory that has shaken the very roots of the rural society uprooting the farmers in their traditional bastion. Indian farmers are known to be as simple, honest, hard working people. Agriculture is an activity steeped in traditions, age old customs which had been sincerely followed, meticulously observed as with a sense of devotion. These have conditioned the lives, their outlook and the world view of the rural people and more so the farmers. The tradition governed farmers in the country were suddenly exposed to a series of economic reforms during the last decade of the twentieth century

Farmers in Anantapur district were not unfamiliar with the frequent spells of drought conditions forcing crop loss and the resultant dismal conditions. They were socialized to cope up with vagaries of nature with scarce water resources with suitable crop patterns dietary habits and a style of life more suitable to their habitat. The globalization and the changes it brought about kindled hope for a better lives and they all shifted to cash and commercial crops without the requisite know how and community support. The counsel of the elders have gives a go by in their ambitious pursuit of commercial cropping thus ending in a debt trap and their ultimate suicide in an chronic anomic situation over a period of years of continuous hard ship forced by loss of crop and the vagaries of nature.

Findings and Discussion

1. In the study that was made in the district of Anantapur, 80 percent of farmers who committed suicides were in the age group of 30-5- years whi9ch means that those who were born just after independence nourished hope of making good fortune by taking agriculture as a fulltime activity with commercial crops particularly groundnut and ended their lives when their aspirations dashed in the sweeping forces of globalization.
2. Analysing the victims by their castes, Forward castes were predominant(48%), backward classes (29%), STs(19%) and SCs (4%).The group of Backward classes who are emerging in the rural Areas in terms of land owning group and the STs who have land are more I the group of victims in The district. These farmers irrespective of their castes have chosen the miserable end considering the insurmountable crises due to their indebtedness.
3. The literacy level of the victims reveals that 19.5 percent were illiterates', 44.5 per cent had only primary education and about 40 per cent had upper primary and above educational levels. The literacy levels of the farmers shows that they were not much educated and the awareness levels for these education is not much. These famers go by here say and their traditional

- beliefs rather than reasoning and science. Being simple and largely governed by beliefs and emotions they have taken the extreme step of taking away their lives without searching for any alternative means of livelihood.
4. Going by the amount of debts, 69 per cent of the victims had a debt of less than 1 lakh while 30.5 per cent had debts ranging between 1-2 lakhs and only one had debt above 2-3 lakhs. The range of debts only shows that the amount of debt is not much in terms of their economic value but the valuable lives were taken away in a moment of desperation. More than the economic loss in terms of crop loss or the drying of the bore wells, the sense of status loss and prestige as a small or marginal farmer which seemed to have been eroded at the act of borrowing and the non repayment in time to the private money lenders is what drove the poor simple farmer to desperation.
 5. Rural people are known for their simple, sincere, hard working nature. They are also forth right, outspoken and also impulsive in maintaining certain norms and values handed down from the past. The sudden surge wrought in by the forces of globalization is something they are ill equipped to take and hence buckled down in the pressure that it brought forth. The society on its part did not try to reciprocate the social obligation of the 'Anna Data' instead it cheated him with spurious pesticides and fake seeds and fleeced him for the hybrid seeds which lured him with bountiful crop. The farmer who had food security through the traditional seeds now made to depend upon the seeds which promised him high yield to clear away debts accumulated over the years. The seeds could not be set apart for the subsequent cultivation and hence the farmers were bereft of the traditional practice of setting apart seeds which sustained them at times of drought. In the absence of Institutional credit these farmers had to depend on the money lenders who fleeced them with interest rates which soared over the years.
 6. The present generation of farmers, who were born after independence of the nation so they nursed aspirations of the new spirit of Independence. Emboldened by the planned initiatives, the farmers aspired higher returns by switching over to commercial crops without taking into consideration the limitations at hand. The capital intensive agriculture did not yield the desired yields due to the quality of seeds, pesticides and the drought added on to misery of the farmers during the years 2001-2003 which resulted in loss of crops forcing the farmers to borrow for the coming years. In anticipation of better yield only landed them in a debt trap never to recover only to end their poor lives in suicide.
 7. Another important feature about the farmer is their simple nature. They are known for their imitative behaviour of fellows as an aspect of cultural

homogeneity typical to folk society. In all their lives rural people are known to blindly imitate others in dress, language, ways of behaviour, worldview, problem perception and solutions in which one could clearly discern fatalism and attribution to beliefs Agriculture is a an activity that is carried on in distant places without much interaction with other fellow farmers. In the modern era where in the rural areas are also known for politicization on the basis of parties have all added on to the seclusion and isolation of the farmers from their own groups.

8. The media socialization towards conspicuous consumption also has influenced the rural people ever since the satellite channels had began imposing the global cultures, their lifestyles, values and consumerism. Enticed by the glittering world of pleasures as beamed by the televisions kindled even the rural people to crave for conspicuous consumption in other words triggering higher expenditure on quality education and lifestyles warranting greater expenditure leading to inevitable debt bondage. The life styles underwent sea of changes ever since the televisions began round the clock beaming of programs. Even the very idea of farmers taking recourse to suicides were given wide publicity in TV and radio longer hours by the political parties to gain political mileage but in the process it has socialized the farmers to resort to suicide. The important component that has caused severe distress among the farming community in India and in the state of A.P. in particular can be broadly listed out as follows:

- Distress conditions related to drought and failure of rain fall quite often;
- Loss of crops, due to inferior quality of inputs and timely non availability of
- Inputs;
- Adoption of new technology, with inadequate knowledge and expertise;
- Sudden attack of pests and diseases;
- Yield of productivity of loss due to the above reasons or any other reason;
- Market prices crash due to bulk arrivals in the market or other extraneous factors;
- Non availability of proper marketing infrastructure and imperfection in the
- Existing markets;
- Mounting credit burden, debt trap and consequent financial non-viability;
- Interlocked input-credit product markets;

- Failure of extension services to advice at the proper time about farm operations.
- Counseling failure by the institutions and breaking off traditional village institutions.

Conclusions

The process of globalization has set in a total transformation of the lifestyles of the developing societies affecting them in varied ways. The quantum and the trajectory of forces unleashed by globalization are too much to be absorbed by the simple, rural realm which has begun to stagger unable to bear the velocity of change. The suicide of the farmers is an indicator of the social pathology set in the Indian rural society which is trying to engulf the agrarian and weaving sectors which were once the vibrant mainstays of rural economy. The larger chunk of farming community now finds itself socially excluded in the new trajectory of change and development precipitated by globalization and its concomitant measures of economic reforms. The government cannot be a mute spectator to the miseries of the rural masses who are now in the cross roads knowing not where to go and what to do. It's time that the government wakes up to stem the alienation of the vibrant community of farmers and save them from the path of suicide.

The reasons for farmers' suicide are multiple and intertwined with social, economic, psychological and cultural in nature. The solution to the problem of farmers' suicide should encompass a totalitarian approach wherein the unorganized farming community, are first organized into farmers' guilds to protect and promote farmers interests so as to evolve cohesion among themselves so as to face challenges through a concerted effort with the able support of the society in a sense of reciprocal responsibility in the Jajmani sense. We cannot afford to ignore the large chunk of about 70% in agrarian sector. The government should balance the forces of globalization with a focus on the agrarian character of our society.

It is heartening to note that the incidence of farmers' suicide has since comedown beginning with the year 2004 when the congress party has come into power. A series of measures initiated has given confidence in the farming community. NREP, waiver off loans to farmers, free electricity to farmers, series of irrigation projects has created hope in the minds of the farmers that the government has become sensitive and responsive to their problems. The popular welfare measures such as housing, health, 25ps Interest have rekindled and rejuvenated the rural community which was feeling neglected and isolated. The forces of globalization which drove the rural people to the fringes of society are now in the process of social inclusion, thanks to policies of the congress government. The government in A.P has certainly remembered the Gandhian

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Talisman to wipe away tears from every eye of its citizen through various schemes in Sarvodaya spirit and brought in the social inclusion of the rural community particularly the community of farmers. Hope these initiatives taken are not withdrawn in the melt down, which is underway extending its tentacles world wide.

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Table No. I: Year wise incidence of suicides in Anantapur District

	Frequency	Percent
2001	47	23.5
2002	41	20.5
2003	56	28.0
2004	41	20.5
2005	15	7.5
Total	200	100.0

Table No. II: Age wise Distribution of Suicide Victims

Age	No. of Victims	Percent
< 30	20	10.0
31-40	68	34.0
41-50	72	36.0
51-60	32	16.0
60>	8	4.0
Total	200	100.0

Table No. III: Caste Wise Distribution of suicide victims

Caste	No. of Victims	Percent
OC	96	48.0
BC	58	29.0
SC	8	4.0
ST	38	19.0
Total	200	100.0

Table No. IV: Literacy levels of Victims

Educational Stats	No. of Victims	Percent
No Schooling	39	19.5
Primary(1 – 5)	89	44.5
Upper Primary(6 -7) 10 th	71	35.5
Intermediate Degree	1	.5
Total	200	100.0

Table No. V: Type of Suicide

	Frequency	Percent
Individual	195	97.5
Couple	1	.5
Family	4	2.0
Total	200	100.0

Table No. VI: Illnesses of Victims

	Frequency	Percent
No Illness	35	17.5

BP	1	.5
Sugar	8	4.0
Acidity	48	24.0
Depression	108	54.0
Total	200	100.0

Table No.VII: Reasons for Suicide

	Frequency	Percent
Water for crop	81	40.5
Failure of wells	15	7.5
Debts	102	51.0
Others	2	1.0
Total	200	100.0

Table No. VIII: Contributory Reasons for Suicide

	Frequency	Percent
Economical	191	95.5
Psychological	8	4.0
Sociological	1	.5
Total	200	100.0

Table No. IX: Amount of debt incurred

	Frequency	Percent
< 1 Lakh	138	69.0
1-2 Lakhs	61	30.5
2-3 Lakhs	1	.5
Total	200	100.0

Table No.X: Place of suicide

	Frequency	Percent
Home	13	6.5
Field	171	85.5
Forest	3	1.5
Open Place	13	6.5
Total	200	100.0